

ORGANIZING ROTARY MOVEMENT IMPROVEMENT METHODS.

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Abstract; An increase in the production of cars leads to an increase in the intensity of traffic and an increase in road congestion. It is characteristic that the growth rate of the traffic intensity is much faster than the growth rate of the length of the road network. In this regard, traffic conditions are deteriorating, the number of traffic accidents is increasing, time losses are increasing, and the efficiency of the road is decreasing. In such conditions, the problem of improving the road network is particularly urgent.

One of the most dangerous parts of highways is their level crossings, where traffic accidents are concentrated, the speed of vehicles is reduced and the traffic capacity is significantly reduced. The analysis of statistics on accidents shows that about 18% of all traffic accidents recorded on the roads are concentrated in one-level intersections. Traffic requirements are best met with different level crossings. However, their construction is associated with high costs, and they are cost-effective only at high traffic speeds.

Key words; circulation action, conflict, destruction, conflict, yth, feature, passive security, traffic speed

Analysis and results; Circulation of action common features. Circulation movement is one bilaterally of action separately status and collision of points the number and danger level reduce principle work squeal This method road at intersections and especially complicated to the configuration have has been and many of the streets intersected in places is used. Round of action main signs opposite intersection of points lack of and them joining and branch with replacement

Circulation roads with intersected in the floodplains the speed mandatory decrease is provided and action control to do necessity no will be done. This attitude with circulation roads self in order soluvshi that is called

Circulation of action to himself special Features:

1. controversial intersection points little
2. correct to shares relatively the speed reduce
3. stops number shortening means transport of means delay reduce
4. of action continuity;
5. traffic light in order to put current reach that's it hash how expenses;

Characteristics because of circulation roads another in order not placed to connections than significant level is safer. However, it is round movement each always too possible and to the goal according to not Obstacle transport of the center suspected area, as well as pedestrians of movement complexity and inconvenience to be can

Figure 1. Circulation of action security islands with equipment.

Ring road shorharas when designing main attention of the plan geometric to the elements and of intersection vertical order focus need Plan of the elements dimensions right from choosing to the following dependent: in the shorrahada to see conditions; of the driver whole shorrahada and intersected of roads direction perception of arrival correctness; cars between mutually effect conditions; movement speed of these factors all accident level and whole splash transfer ability solution action effect shows. Vehicle stability level, pass time and speed vertical order right to choose depend

Plan and vertical planning to the size to be placed requirements compliance to do car ways at the intersection movement conditions in improvement solution action factor is considered Circles main elements of the following consists of, ring of the road width length ring to the way entry 11 and enter width 10; ring from the way swelling 5 and to squeeze width 6 and 7 row annular commute in the part transversely slopes mating; to the right turning cars that's it special lane 3; connecting (intersection) road.

Placement types. Main geometric elements in the calculation basis has been main principle two intersection roads between ringed commute in the part entrance and ringed car of streams constant respectively merger and later mutually is connected. Motor transport of streams mutually connection that's it conditions provide big central islands ($D \geq 100 \div 120$ m). circulation roads to build demand does Big central islands has been circulation roads wide not used. of the islands medium diameter is $25 \div 80$ m circulation on the roads car of streams self in order soluvshi interval movement is set, in which joining in the zone from currents one in action to advantage have

Man central islands ($D \leq 25$ m) and to the waterfall inputs extended circulation directions too self in order soluvshi intermittent transport flow with separate stands and high to power have Equal didn't happen car ways cut in transition more active in the direction movement conditions improve that's it circulation turnovers oval, elliptical or transit transport that's it slotted central island with in order is put

Projecting security of the islands length is given in table 1.

Table-1

Road category	Project circle length, m	
	Recommendation length	Most less length
I	65	50

II	60	47
III	55	30
IV	45	20

Conclusion and Suggestions; Circulation movement places to use experience that's it showed that the offer given our advice to paint the following to the advantages have we will be:

- one at the point out of four more than the way cut in transition action reasonable organize to do possible;
- movement in order put that's it hash how expenses no
- opposition points separation, low relative speed and circulation of the road sharp kidneys (mutual link) action safety to increase help gives;
- cars by time the loss of one different level traditional to shorahas than Ansha little
- in the waterfall movement order simple and drivers that's it understandable;
- one different level another kind of to shorahas relatively to the cheek turning maneuver perform that's it good conditions provides;
- ring intersection device that's it capital expenses different level to intersections relatively significant level less;
- person central islands and at the entrance increased row circulation roads different level of streams capacity with comparable high to power have

Circulation on the roads; Road in the floodplains to the drivers of the route main of points location, shoraha across movement order, pedestrians transition of places location and of the situation another features about in advance informed to do need This to the goal road signs belongs to placement (GOST 10807-78 " Road signs. General technical conditions " and GOST 23457-79 " Road movement organize of reaching technical tools. Usage the rules of " boisha " and of roads commute part designation through reach can

Approaches to paint movement intensity ratio, of motion directions to paint distribution, intersected of roads economic importance and circulation on the roads movement feature looking, moving organize of doing different different options acceptance to be done can

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